

The Task-Based Approach to Online Language Learning: An Example of Practice

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ABSTRACT

Distance learning, face-to-face learning, mediated communication, virtual classrooms, e-tasks, are all terms that have recently been at the heart of the preoccupations of practitioners and of the research community in Education Sciences and Didactics. But what exactly is it about? And what does it have to do with language teaching and learning? In what forms is it relevant to use these Internet-based devices? What changes does this imply for the teacher and what is his/her role from now on? These are some of the questions that this article will attempt to answer. The focus is on language learning in an e-learning teaching device and the conditions that must be met for this mode of learning to be effective.

KEYWORDS: Distance, face-to-face, languages, CECRL, actional approach.

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the teaching-learning devices proposed within the Moroccan education system have evolved with the influence of a new relationship to knowledge generated by the emergence of new technologies. Moreover, lever 20 of the Strategic Vision 2015-2030 emphasizes the strong institutional will to promote the integration of ICTE in education in Morocco. In particular, we note that the different types of courses offered have moved from a format based essentially on the face-to-face aspect to a format conducted at a distance. In fact, to ensure continuity of teaching and learning in the face of the Covid-19 health crisis, several types of technology-based training have replaced face-to-face teaching. Given this particular context, this article raises the fundamental question of the relevant and critical use of technology, in other words, the impact and implications of technology in the language learning process in an environment where the use of technology is driven by the need to ensure pedagogical continuity.

This article aims to take stock of the multiple possibilities offered by e-learning teaching within the framework of an action-oriented perspective and of the conditions to be met in order for these opportunities to achieve the desired objectives. To do so, we will first address the theoretical aspect of designing pedagogical and didactic practices of a distance learning teaching device, and then we will

highlight, through a practical example of the use of technological tools, the implications of this type of device on language learning.

II. REMOTE VS FACE TO FACE

In order to bring more clarity to our remarks, let us begin by defining fully online (distance) training as a "distance presence" device, an expression taken from the title of a book by Weissberg, (1999). In an article, Mangenot (2002) shows the gradual constitution of a learning community in a fully distance master's course in French as a foreign language, revealed by the content of certain e-mails, forum messages or answers to end-of-year questionnaires. It can be estimated that four conditions must be met for the "encounter" to take place: tools for sharing (in the example above, forums), pedagogical support (in the case above, provided by the teacher who wrote the course, roughly at the rate of half a day per week), a common timeline (not necessarily synchronous), and open pedagogical activities (in the case above, two or three tasks per month - over six months - were to be carried out on a different forum for each task, with students being able to do their work at any time within this monthly limit).

A. Media communication

The most apparent specificity in e-learning teaching is that all pedagogical communication will take place through digital devices, computers, tablets, smartphones, etc. This is known as "mediated pedagogical communication" (Peraya, 2000).

One question immediately arises: will this mediated educational communication take place in a synchronous or asynchronous mode? The synchronous mode is obviously the one that comes closest to the face-to-face course and modern tools make it fairly easy to have a dozen people communicate online, in a video conference (Zoom, Microsoft Teams, Google Hangout, Adobe Connect). That said, one of the main reasons for opting for e-learning is the freedom of time and place that such a form of teaching brings: learning when you want and where you want. The synchronous mode allows freedom of place but not of time, since the people wishing to exchange online will have to make a specific appointment, as in the case of a face-to-face course.

If one adopts an essentially asynchronous mode, then there is a wide choice of tools, such as blogs, wikis, forums, e-mail, etc. But it is not enough to choose the right tool for what one wants to have learners do, one must also establish a method of use (for example: form groups and open a discussion on the subject of the course). But it is not enough to choose the right tool for what you want the learners to do, you also have to establish an instruction manual (e.g.: Form groups and open a discussion on the chat room) and a timeline for their use (e.g.: such and such a task is to be done by Tuesday evening).

In the current situation, combining the two modes for optimal exploitation of technological resources would be the most efficient option in such circumstances. We will elaborate on this point later.

B. Design and conduct a course

If we exclude the Language Resource Center or Independent Learning Center type of system (Albero, 2000, Barbot, 2000, Rivens Mompean, 2013), where, in principle, it is the learner who leads his or her own learning with the help of advisors, the face-to-face language course is led by a teacher who tells the learners what they must do throughout the session; the teacher notices very quickly if there is a misunderstanding of the instructions and can readjust at any time. The teacher has several techniques for correcting: he or she can immediately correct an erroneous formulation (with the risk of cutting off the learner's momentum), note the error and point it out later, ask the group to be attentive to language problems, rephrase an erroneous sentence while including it in the pedagogical communication, etc. The face-to-face teacher can also have the learners work in small groups (possibly in front of a computer) and move from group to group, then have each group present their work

(possibly with the help of presentation software). Some teachers produce very detailed preparation sheets before their classes, others leave more room for improvisation, and still others follow a teaching guide provided by the method used.

Online, it's a different story. France Henri, a Quebec expert on distance learning, believes that one of the advantages of mediated devices is that they allow teacher-designers to anticipate learning:

"The mediatization approach requires the teacher to re-conceptualize his teaching. From now on, he or she must plan, anticipate and prepare well in advance the learning scenario, the reference documents, the work and communication tools that the students will use, the instructions and advice that will guide the learning, the support and follow-up mechanisms, the evaluation methods, etc. (Henri, 2003)".

France Henri considers this development to be positive insofar as it inevitably leads to a certain reflexivity - and even to some pooling - of pedagogical resources; the course, being written and online, can more easily be consulted by other teachers. There may also be some resistance to the sharing of information between teachers, for example, the loss of the theatrical aspect of face-to-face teaching.

C. Four differences between distance and face-to-face training

In order to better design the e-learning teaching device, we should first be aware of its characteristics. We quote below the most important ones according to Mangenot and Soubrié (2010).

Giving instructions: these must be extremely clear and precise (including deadlines for completion and the expected form and length), knowing that the learner will be alone in front of his computer when he reads them.

There are an almost infinite number of resources available on the Internet, both in terms of support documents and aids, and it would be absurd to do without them. That said, the risk is to waste a lot of time finding the right source. For the aids, there are sites that are more stable than others, and this must be taken into account so that the course can be reused from one year to the next. In this sense, the teacher will rely on reference sites that often update the data made available so that the learners can always refer to them.

Tutoring is a form of individualized teaching assistance, which is offered either to accompany a learner who is experiencing difficulties, or to provide specific, complementary or distance training. It can take many forms, depending on the degree of autonomy already acquired by the learners, but it is clear that its volume (the time the teacher spends following the learners online) and its remuneration depend on institutional choices.

The communication tools for completing the task (and the tutor's help) also tend to multiply uncontrollably.

To summarize, the online language teacher will have to carry out actions that are quite different from those of the face-to-face teacher, some of which are much more time-consuming than those required to conduct a face-to-face course, in the sense that the teacher will have to test his or her device beforehand, in addition to the continuous training (of the teacher) necessary to adapt to the digital tool, which alone creates certain difficulties for teachers.

D. Forms of self-study

Another question that can be asked is the self-directed dimension that can be included (or not) in an e-learning course. Compared to a face-to-face class, it is clear that the learner's choices are more extensive. They can consult some resources, leave others aside. They can choose when they work, in the most frequent case of teaching-learning devices that are predominantly asynchronous. If the scenario of the course provides for it, he can choose to work alone or with others. Concerning the corrections, the tutor can, for example, point out his mistakes and then let him correct himself.

III. THE TASK-BASED APPROACH AND DISTANCE LEARNING TEACHING

A. The task-based approach, the actional perspective

The task-based approach originated in Anglo-Saxon language teaching, as shown by the pioneering work of the Australian David Nunan, published in 1989, as well as the very comprehensive work of Rod Ellis (2003). It was then taken up by the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR).

The dominant approach to language teaching and learning for about 25 years has been the so-called "communicative" approach, this term referring to a double level: the speech acts and communication situations that the learners had to master were those prevailing in real life on the one hand, and the communication in class had to be as authentic as possible on the other hand. It was a question of going beyond the limits of teaching that was too focused on the repetition/memorization of structures. But within the communicative approach itself, a certain number of Anglo-Saxon didacticians, from the mid-1980s onwards, proposed a variation, the task-based language teaching approach (Nunan, 1989, Ellis, 2003): the central idea was that of an emphasis on meaning (having students carry out really meaningful activities) rather than on form (grammar, lexicon, etc.). Subsequently, emphasis was also placed on the fact that the task should have a well-defined outcome against which its success could be assessed.

In fact, since the year 2000, the actional perspective has entered the field of EFL didactics. The actional perspective adds a dimension to the communicative approach. A real dimension: to communicate in order to act, and moreover, to interact.

"The perspective favored here is, very generally, also of the actional type in that it considers above all the user and the learner of a language as social actors having to accomplish tasks (which are not only linguistic) in circumstances and a given environment, within a particular field of action. If speech acts are carried out in linguistic activities, these activities are themselves inscribed within actions in a social context which alone give them their full meaning. There is a "task" insofar as the action is carried out by one (or more) subject(s) who strategically mobilize(s) the skills at their disposal in order to achieve a given result". (CEFR p.15)

The actional perspective takes into account the fact that we communicate to do something. Teaching follows the same logic: learners will learn to do, and more exactly, will do to learn, hence the importance of the task.

Ellis (2003) pointed out the importance of organizing the contributions of the learners and the teacher in the completion of the task:

"A task is a plan of work, primarily meaning-oriented, leading learners to handle language in a way that is close to real life, may involve one or more of the four skills, involves the learner in the cognitive process, and has a clearly identifiable outcome to determine whether the task has been successfully completed." (Ellis, 2003)

The definition that will be used in an e-learning teaching perspective differs from Ellis's on one particular point: for there to be a task, there must be a production on the part of the learners, oral or written, in class or online, monological or dialogical (without production, there is no online exchange and therefore no social dimension)

B. Specificity of the tasks in the online action-oriented perspective

The task in the actional perspective: The Council of Europe (2001) has advocated an "actional perspective" which consists of giving meaning to the learning activity itself by involving learners in tasks related to proven social practices (Soubrié, 2008). The question of meaning is no longer considered only from a linguistic or even discursive point of view, but also from a praxeological point of view: "If speech acts are carried out in language activities, which alone give them their full meaning [...]" (Council of Europe, 2001, p.15). The evolution comes especially from this link that we try to establish between the language class and the outside world, a link already put forward by project-based pedagogy.

In this sense, Mangenot & Soubrié (2010) assert that in languages, designing and conducting an online course should be based on tasks (actional approach) or, more rarely, on projects. The implementation of the task is based on a certain number of components: one or more **supporting documents, pedagogical activities** (tasks) materialized by **instructions** specifying the expected production (written or

oral), **deadlines** and **work methods** (individual, in pairs, in groups), aids to implementation (tutoring, internet links, tool cards), **evaluation methods**. It is thus a good principle for the realization of online learning teaching devices.

Specificities of tasks using the Internet: Learning tasks play a fundamental role in technological environments. They determine the way in which learners will confront course materials and the forms of knowledge construction that will result.

Figure 1. Olivier & Herrington, 2001

Three elements of the task are specific to the use of new technologies: the two main ones are the starting medium and the means of communication between learners. The production can also have a multimedia character or be published on the social web.

As already noted by Mangenot & Louveau (2006), the crucial element of a well-designed task is the link between the medium and the production. In the case of tasks using the Internet (e-tasks), we can specify this idea by saying that the production activity(ies) requested from the learners (through the instructions) must be strongly linked to the multimedia medium serving as a resource:

- On the semantic level: the meaning of the activity must be consistent with the meaning conveyed by the medium
- Linguistically: the material must contain language elements that can be used in the production activity

C. Task design in an e-learning teaching device

When designing a task, it is important to design a communication scenario in case online interactions are planned:

- Who will communicate with whom (class group or subgroups)?
- With the help of which tool(s)?
- At what rate (synchronous and/or asynchronous) and how often?
- With what intervention from the teacher?

The pedagogical scenario: The expression "pedagogical scenario" or "learning scenario" is very much linked to open and distance learning and therefore to mediatization: as the teacher is not present at the time when the learning activities are carried out, it is necessary to define and formalize them

much more precisely than is usually done for the face-to-face classroom. Several definitions of the pedagogical scenario can be cited. For de Lièvre, Quintin & Depover (2002), it is "a temporal organization of pedagogical activities arranged in order to reach the set objectives as efficiently as possible". Pernin & Lejeune are more precise on the question of roles, resources, tools and services:

"A pedagogical scenario represents the description, carried out a priori or a posteriori, of the unfolding of a learning situation or learning unit aiming at the appropriation of a precise set of knowledge, by specifying the roles, the activities as well as the knowledge manipulation resources, tools and services necessary for the implementation of the activities. (Pernin & Lejeune, 2004) "

In the field of languages, Nissen (2006) proposes a definition that better takes into account communication.

In all these definitions, "scenario" refers to a fairly large part, probably on the order of a complete course. Whatever its size, an instructional scenario can be defined as a set of tasks to which one would add a number of details essentially related to mediatization.

In any case, it seems crucial to include in the pedagogical design what Tricot & Plégat-Soutjis (2003), in a very detailed article on the design of distance learning systems using technologies, call a "supervision scenario", i.e. a forecast of the online exchanges likely to occur. Other authors refer to a "supervision scenario" (de Lièvre et al., 2006), to designate the roles that the tutor will have to fulfil.

Tutoring: It is generally considered that distance tutoring implies a certain number of functions (or types of tutorial interventions, Denis, 2003), not necessarily fulfilled by the same people and not always ensured in each device. According to the typologies of Denis, 2003 and Bourdet, 2006, there are six main functions of the tutor:

Technology assistant: learners need time to adapt to the digital environment. Someone must be available to answer any problems encountered, even if only in terms of login and password. This function is sometimes assigned to a hotline, accessible by phone or email.

Content expert: the expert is usually the teacher who wrote (or filmed) the course, who may or may not be one of the tutors.

Methodological advisor: knowing how to organize oneself at a distance is important, and the instructions themselves must contribute to this organizational help. But the tutor also has a role to play, if only to remind the students of deadlines, to ensure that the work is properly distributed, to advise them on which method to use rather than another, to point out which website might be of help, etc.

Tutor: The tutor is sometimes the designer of the tasks, without being the editor of the course. In other cases, the tutor can adapt the tasks. Sometimes, we are not dealing with tasks but with a project: the tutor will then play more of a role of adviser and facilitator in relation to the course.

Facilitator, who can sometimes tend towards a role of parity (a role defined by Bourdet, 2006, as "support for progress, participation in the task as an actor"). More generally, it is a matter of ensuring a good relational climate, encouraging and (re)motivating.

Evaluator, again, the summative evaluation function (grading) can be assigned to someone other than the tutor. But there is often a form of formative evaluation, during the process, for example when learners are asked to keep an online log.

Aids for the realization of a task: One of the essential elements that is added to the design of a task in e-learning teaching is the development of task aids.

The first type of assistance to be provided to learners concerns task guidance: the instructions must be extremely precise, indicating in particular the expected production and its length.

A well thought-out task will usually be divided into several steps. It is therefore essential that at each stage the learner has clear instructions at his disposal, enabling him to know precisely what he has to do, with which tools and which materials. One of the interests of working with digital technology is to free the teacher from the role of direct provider of instructions by transposing them into a techno-pedagogical tool, for example a platform that will be the direct interface of the learner and thus allow each learner to progress at his own pace and according to his own choices. In this sense, the learner will have, for example, deadlines for the completion of tasks designed by the teacher.

The second type of help is related to tutoring. One of the important roles of the language tutor is to provide corrective feedback (Denis, 2003 and de Bourdet, 2006).

A final point to consider is the subtasks or microtasks, which are intended to help with the main action. They can be lexical, grammatical, phonetic aids, examples of texts, rhetorical advice, etc. Usually, a link to online dictionaries, grammars and translators is provided.

The subtasks are very often closed, in the sense that they do not call for open-ended production, which should necessarily be subject to human feedback. We use an exercise generator such as Hot Potatoes, Moodle's "Quiz", Quizlet, Quizziz, or Kahoot, which make it possible to design MCQs, fill-in-the-blank exercises, matching exercises, and puzzles based on authentic content found elsewhere on the Web, with the possibility of making links within the exercise itself. This principle, which makes it

possible to develop interesting written and oral comprehension activities, is used in a certain number of FLE (French as a Foreign Language) educational sites.

Considering that the task and the pedagogical scenario belong to two different levels of granularity, in order to better take into account the choice of collective or individual work modalities, We will therefore define the "cybertask" as an arrangement of learning activities (called by some "micro-tasks" or "sub-tasks") tending towards the realization of an identifiable main action concretized by one (or more) production(s) / open verbal interaction(s), production or interaction themselves supported by supporting documents. The pedagogical scenario is then itself made up of one or more cyber-tasks relating to the same theme or situation, combined with a communication scenario and providing for a chronology of exchanges.

IV. EXAMPLE OF SPECIFICATIONS FOR DESIGNING AND RUNNING ONLINE COURSES

To illustrate the above, we will now present some tasks from online courses, with their respective communication scenarios. The first part will focus on the specifications illustrating the different essential elements of a distance learning course. The second part will present some tasks based on the scripting of the latter.

A. Specifications for designing and running an online course

During the elaboration of these specifications, we referred to the work of Mangenot and Louveau (2006) in order to adapt the objectives, the tasks and the technical means implemented to achieve them.

Table.1 Online Training Tools

Selected format:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Virtual classroom - synchronous • Asynchronous tutoring
Platform chosen for the virtual classroom:	TEAMS / Zoom
Possible collaboration and editing platforms to use for tutoring:	<p>We can use Teams or other platforms:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Google classroom • Edmodo • Padlet

Possible applications to be used for tutoring and virtual classrooms:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Collaborative word processing <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Google docs Videos <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Powtoon ☐ Video scribe ☐ Tellagami ☐ Edpuzzle Quizzes/surveys <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Mentimeter ☐ Quizziz ☐ Kahoot ☐ Learning apps ☐ Edpuzzle ☐ Google forms ☐ Moodle ☐ Verbal planet ☐ Italki Visuals and presentations <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Canva ☐ Google slides ☐ Brainstorming ☐ Answergarden Stories <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Inklewriter free ☐ Storybird
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- Define the optimal duration of a virtual classroom session (or at least the duration of the activities)
- Choose the objectives, content and activities to be done in the virtual classroom.
- Implement an approach that allows learners to be more autonomous and effective in using knowledge.
- Think about assessment (diagnostic, formative and summative).

Preparing for the virtual classroom: The virtual classroom is a space that needs to be well prepared before starting the course, just like preparing a face-to-face course. Nevertheless, the teacher will be obliged to manage a technological tool that may block many possible scenarios in face-to-face, i.e. peer or small group work. The teacher will have to prepare his teaching sequence, his resources and his interventions by taking into account the following features:

- Audio and video **interventions** by the teacher and learners
- **Document** sharing and collaboration on these documents (virtual board)
- **Video** sharing and interaction on these videos (YouTube type)
- **Screen** sharing = all or one window or tab of the chrome browser
- Global and individual chat: for sharing **links to external applications**
- Share **surveys and quizzes with** results
- **Recording of** the virtual class

A pedagogical sequence in an e-learning course must contain the different steps with links to external documents and tools such as websites and collaborative documents (documents that are open and can be consulted at any time during the virtual class). Just like in the classroom, the teacher must plan an alternating rhythm to maintain attention: a virtual classroom activity should not last more than 15 minutes. In this sense, the teacher must plan to give time for reflection and group work without forgetting the production task.

Facilitate the virtual classroom: Before running the virtual classroom, the teacher will have to do all the technical checks, i.e. the audio and sound, the video (camera, framing, background, lighting and posture), and the opening of all the web pages necessary to load the materials on the software chosen to run the virtual classroom (see table n° 1).

During the virtual classroom launch phase, the teacher first displays a previously designed welcome (waiting) screen (presentation/technical reminders and rules/anticipatory support to arouse the learners' curiosity: photo, expression, quote, etc./reminder of notions, etc.) He will then proceed to share the webcam and microphone to greet the learners and to do a sound and image check, while challenging the

In this specification, we have chosen four main steps to conduct an online training:

Figure 2. Four steps to online training

Prepare a scenario: The design of the scenario for an e-learning teaching device must follow an actional approach as the courses and the different technological tools currently available prove to be suitable. The scenario, recommended for our article, must contain an articulation between asynchronous tutoring and the virtual classroom. In this sense, it is necessary to think well about the tool for the realization of the task:

-Choose the objectives, content, and activities to be done in the tutorial (comprehension, identification, production). Among these, choose what will be done before and what will be done after the virtual class.

learners and proposing solutions to technical problems, if any exist

In both face-to-face and distance learning, each class is federated by an essential rule. For example:

- Announce that to avoid interference/noise problems on the learner's side, everyone will have to turn off their microphone when they are not speaking virtual classroom software is now able to detect when a person is not speaking and automatically turns off their microphone to avoid spreading ambient noise.

- Explain that the "hand up" option should be used to speak when someone else is speaking.

- Remind them that they need to get into the right mood: ask them to be quiet, close the internet pages, put the phone on standby, etc. before starting the session!

-All of these steps are a start to the actual facilitation of the course. In the following, we propose a set of steps for conducting the virtual classroom:

a- Home and Icebreaker

b- Animate the course according to the pedagogical sequence with all the tools: presentation, interaction on presentation, audio, screen sharing, polls...

- o Prepare a comprehension quiz and share it with learners
- o Check the understanding of the instruction
- o Inform learners of the response procedures and time limits
- o Launch/share video or written document
- o Let the learners check their answers.

c- Manage interactions: controlled exchanges (e.g., in chat), spontaneous exchanges (e.g., via audio), group exchanges.

d- Ensure that learners are following along, which allows for formative evaluation. To do this, we will use surveys and quizzes to check the concepts acquired or to ask for the group's opinion on an explanation.

e- Conclude the virtual class by reviewing the fundamental points through a debriefing activity without forgetting the preparation of the next virtual class.

Facilitating the tutoring: As already explained, tutoring is done in an asynchronous way. It consists of monitoring activities and offering help and feedback to learners. This phase allows for individual evaluation of the learners and for general assessments.

B. Practical example of a scenario for e-learning teaching

This scenario is an excerpt from the textbook *Cosmopolite 2* for adults/students at B1.1 level. The objectives are as follows:

- Pragmatics: Identify ranking criteria / Perform a ranking
- Linguistics: Words and expressions to describe a classification, prepositional verbs to talk about

expatriation, expressions of warning

In the following, we propose a summary of the whole didactic unit, and we will specify afterwards, an example for the part access to the meaning. The didactic unit, put forward in the following, is based on an actional approach. The tasks to be carried out throughout this unit: anticipation, reading comprehension (EC), location and conceptualization, are the micro-tasks to reach the final objective which is the written production. Throughout this unit, we have tried to implement collaboration between learners and this through web tools such as "the interactive whiteboard", the use of "WhatsApp" which allows to have a social link with the rest of the class and even with the teacher.

Lesson 1: Identify ranking and performing a classification.

Activities:

- Learner welcome with welcome screen + call
- Review of the first session's assignment
- Question and answer about the digital manual

Anticipation:

-Display a PPT with images of world capitals to introduce the theme.

-Ask the students to speculate (either individually or via the chat room) about the purpose of the poster = a competition organized by the RATP to select the city that moves.

Explanation of objectives (PPT)

CE:

Display document 1: reading and explanation of instructions with work methods and time allowed:

List the pluses and minuses of your hometown.

Record of interventions: round table

Write the names of the pairs in boxes on the whiteboard

Give the instructions for the activity: read document 1 and list the 12 criteria used to classify the cities.

-What criteria are essential?

Which criteria are original? Why are they original?

The pairs work together and write the criteria in their box.

<https://learningapps.org/display?v=pyht0hvpk20>

This was an aperçu of some of the activities that we tried in this unit. We based our work on a vision in which we have a few steps.

In the following we try to propose a vision of what could be the course of an activity of comprehension (access to the meaning) of a document.

Step 1: technical ritual

-Welcome learners with a previously developed welcome screen.

-Activate the webcam and microphone.

-Greet learners as they log in, calling on them individually to ensure that the equipment is working properly.

-Propose solutions to technical problems if any.

-Announce the rules of the virtual classroom.

-Inform learners that the session is being recorded and click on record for a later replay.

Step 2: teaching ritual:

- Begin with an icebreaker activity such as the Chinese portrait, which consists of the facilitator proposing a list of words such as: animal, color, movie, song, dish, plant, actor, object, clothing, etc. This can be done on the Freehand whiteboard in the virtual classroom where each learner is invited to write or draw their answers. This can be done on the Freehand whiteboard of the virtual classroom where each learner is invited to write or draw their answers.
- Begin the phase of accessing meaning.
- Upstream, import the support document in the Teams file area.
- To launch the activity, open the support document and share the screen with the group of learners.
- Identify the document through the exploitation of Freehand.
- Explain the instructions and specify the time needed to complete the task.
- Pool the results: class
- Display the document as a screen share and ask for 3 volunteers to do the 1st reading, one learner per paragraph, while asking the other learners to write down difficult words on paper or on the conversation tab.
- After the first reading, stop on the difficult words and give some indications, then do a second reading.
- Retrieve the link to the comprehension activity and share it in the chat.
- Explain the instructions and define the time limit.
- Pool the results.
- Ensure understanding.

C. Constraints and limitations

E-learning education offers many advantages including flexibility, time saving for the learner and adaptation to the context of use. It is proving to be an effective system, however taking courses at a distance also has its constraints, limitations and challenges that both the teacher and the learner should face. Here are some of them:

Technical aspect:

- Access to an internet connection
- The need to have a digital device (phone, computer, tablet)
- The need to master the computer tool.
- The design of the activities must be compatible with the different interfaces, which is impossible for the majority of the tools for the synchronous phase
- Paid access to some distance learning platforms.

The educational aspect:

- Time constraint for the design of the training offer with all synchronous sessions and asynchronous activities.
- Lack of face-to-face human contact

- Self-discipline

V. CONCLUSION

Although there are many reasons for setting up a distance learning teaching system, the constraints and limits raised show that it requires particular attention in its design and implementation. Throughout this work, we have dealt with some essential elements for the engineering of such a teaching-learning device based on an actional perspective. Indeed, this type of device requires as much from the learner as from the teacher or tutor, in terms of investment and appropriation. One of the elements to take into consideration is that an authentic actional perspective in the framework of an online language learning teaching device should not ignore the new social genres of activity found on the social web, namely all forms of collaboration through the web. The idea is to actively involve learners in their teaching and learning.

The last remark we would like to make concerns online courses in all their dimensions: any approach that would consist first and foremost in trying to save effort in the design of online courses as well as in their animation. Providing raw resources, no matter how well done, does not constitute teaching and learning. In this sense, it is advisable to adjust the different parameters of the pedagogical scenario as best as possible according to the objectives of the teaching envisaged and the characteristics of the learners, and above all to find the right techno- pedagogical tool for carrying out each task.

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